

Impact Of Consumer Education Programs on Agricultural Consumer Behaviour in Makurdi Metropolis, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study evaluated the impact of consumer education programs on influencing consumer behaviour in Makurdi Metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria. The study was motivated by the increasing concern that many consumers in the area lack adequate knowledge about agricultural products, such as quality, safe handling, labelling, and purchasing decisions, leading to exposure to unsafe and substandard goods. Five objectives guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 350 individuals drawn from consumers, traders, farmers, and agricultural extension officers in the study area. A sample of 188 respondents was selected using the Taro Yamane formula. The results revealed that organised and media-based consumer education programs were the major sources of awareness in the area, with radio and television serving as key channels of communication (Mean = 3.12). Respondents found the information from consumer education programs easy to understand and apply (Mean = 2.88), indicating that message clarity

enhanced participation . It was concluded that consumer education programs have improved consumer awareness in purchasing behaviour . It was recommended that more emphasis be laid on collaborative, media-driven, and continuous education programmes.

Keywords: Consumer Education, Consumer behaviour, Agricultural Products, Makurdi, Nigeria

1.Introduction.

A consumer is someone who uses goods and services including natural resources such as air and water. Most of Agricultural products in Makurdi (fruits and vegetables) were wasted. In today's increasingly complex and fast-changing marketplace, consumers are faced with a wide array of choices, persuasive advertising, and often conflicting product information. Navigating these options requires more than just purchasing power; it demands knowledge, awareness, and critical thinking. This is where consumer education becomes essential. At its core, consumer education is about equipping individuals with the skills and information they need to make informed, responsible, and value-driven choices in the goods and services they buy (Foresi and Strübel, 2025). It empowers people to protect their rights, avoid exploitation, and contribute meaningfully to the economy through conscious consumption (Foresi and Strübel, 2025). Consumer education is globally acknowledged as vital for protecting consumer rights, promoting product safety, and encouraging sustainable consumption. Educated consumers are better able to interpret product information, recognise deceptive practices, and make informed choices, leading to more responsible buying, fewer economic losses, and a fairer marketplace (Foresi and Strübel, 2025).

A key concept closely tied to this discussion is consumer behaviour which refers to the set of actions and decision-making processes that individuals engage in when purchasing and using goods and services. It includes how consumers recognise their needs, search for information, make choices, evaluate products, and respond after purchase (Raji *et al.*, 2024). Consumer behaviour is influenced by a wide range of factors, including personal values, education level, peer influence, media exposure, cultural norms, and past experiences. Consumer education aims to shape behaviour in ways that enhance well-being, prevent exploitation, and support more thoughtful consumption practices (Raji *et al.*, 2024). In Nigeria, despite the presence of key consumer protection agencies like FCCPC,

NAFDAC, and SON, many citizens, particularly in semi-urban and rural areas, lack awareness of their consumer rights (Ezekiel *et al.*, 2021). This information gap leaves them dependent on informal markets with minimal regulation, increasing their vulnerability to exploitation and unsafe products.

This study, therefore, aims to evaluate how effective consumer education programs have been in shaping consumer behaviour Makurdi Metropolis, focusing specifically on Agricultural programs. It will assess levels of awareness, participation, and the extent of behavioural change among residents. The findings will offer evidence-based insights to enhance future program design and delivery. Beyond contributing to academic knowledge, the study addresses a practical issue that directly impacts the daily lives of people in Makurdi and similar communities across Nigeria. Page | 155

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Consumer education programs on agriculture have not changed totally I Makurdi. This was seen in area of agricultural waste due to lack of adequate food processing industries in the state. In recent years, there has been growing concern about how consumers make choices regarding agricultural products such as food items, fertilizers, and farm inputs in Makurdi Metropolis. Many consumers often lack adequate knowledge about product quality, safe handling, labeling, pricing, and proper usage. As a result, they may fall victim to misleading advertisements, fake products, or poor purchasing decisions that affect their health, finances, and overall well-being.

Although government agencies, non-governmental organisations and agricultural extension bodies have introduced various consumer education programs aimed at improving awareness and promoting informed decision-making, the extent to which these programs have influenced actual consumer behaviour remains unclear. In Makurdi, where agriculture plays a vital role in the economy, understanding whether consumer education truly helps individuals make better and safer agricultural purchasing and consumption choices is essential. This knowledge gap has created a need to evaluate the effectiveness of consumer education programs in shaping consumer behaviour within the metropolis.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the impact of consumer education programs on consumer behaviour in Makurdi Metropolis, Benue State.

1.3 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of the study were to:

- I. Determine the types of consumer education programs related to agricultural products in Makurdi.
- II. Find out the level of awareness and participation of consumers in these educational programs.
- III. Determine the influence of consumer education on purchasing and consumption behaviour of agricultural products.
- IV. Identify the challenges affecting the effectiveness of consumer education programs in influencing consumer behaviour.
- V. Suggest strategies for improving the impact of consumer education on agricultural consumer practices in the area.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What are the types of consumer education programs related to agricultural products in Makurdi.
2. What is the level of awareness and participation of consumers in these educational programs.
3. What is the influence of consumer education on purchasing education programs
4. What are the challenges of affecting the effectiveness of consumer education programs.
5. What are the strategies for improving consumer education on agricultural consumer practices in Makurdi.

1.5. Scope of the Study

The study will focus specifically on consumer education programs related to agricultural products, such as food commodities, fertilizers, pesticides, seeds, farm inputs.

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design

The study adapted a descriptive survey research design. This research design is considered appropriate because it has as one of its attributes, the ability to examine current situation in a given place or circumstance and to check the extent to which current practices meet required standard (Uzoagulu, 1998). Descriptive survey was used to study the behaviour of consumers towards accepted principles for agricultural products.

2.2. Population of the study

The study population is 350 people drawn from major stakeholder groups in Makurdi Metropolis. These groups include: household consumers (buyers of agricultural/food products),

farmers, traders/retailers of agricultural products, and agricultural extension/information officers across four locations in Makurdi.

2.3. Sample Size

The sample size for the study was determined using the Taro Yamane formula for finite populations. Thus, the calculated sample size was approximately 188 respondents. Page | 157

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection

Data for this study were collected through a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended and Likert-scale questions, divided into sections to cover demographic information, awareness of consumer education programs, level of participation, and observed behavioural changes. The instrument was designed to be simple, clear, and suitable for individuals with varying literacy levels.

2.5. Validation of the instrument

The instrument was validated by three (3) experts, one of the experts focused on face validity while the other two experts did the content validity.

2.6. Method of data collection

A four-point rating scale was adopted and was assigned the following values:

Strongly agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree/ (D) = 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

Primary data for the study used was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was administered by hand to the respondents and the questionnaire items was received on the spot to avoid loss.

2.7. Data analysis

Data obtained was analyzed by mean scores (\bar{x}). Research question 1, 2 and 3 were analysed using means (\bar{x}). A criterion means of 2.50 was used to decide the acceptance level. All means that are equal to or greater than 2.50 were accepted, while means below 2.50 were rejected.

3. Result And Discussion

Table 1: Mean Response on Awareness and Availability of Consumer Education

S/N	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1	There are organised programs in Makurdi that educate consumers about agricultural products.	3.12	Agree
2	Radio and television programs provide useful information about agricultural products and practices.	3.12	Agree
3	Consumer education programs are provided through local markets and cooperatives	2.79	Agree
4	Agricultural extension officers regularly engage in educating consumers on food safety and quality.	2.45	disagree
5	Schools and community centers organize training on agricultural product use and handling.	2.40	

The findings on the awareness and availability of consumer education in Makurdi Metropolis revealed that respondents generally acknowledged the presence of organized consumer education programs within the study area. The statement that there are organized programs in Makurdi that educate consumers about agricultural products had a mean score of 3.12. Similarly, respondents agreed that radio and television programs provide useful information about agricultural products and practices, also recording a mean of 3.12. Furthermore, the statement that consumer education programs are provided through local markets and cooperatives had a mean of 2.79.

Table 2: Mean Responses on Participation in Consumer Education Programs

S/N	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1	The information from consumer education programs is easy to understand and apply.	2.88	Agree
2	Participation in educational programs has increased the new interest in agricultural products.	2.82	Agree
3	Personally participated in at least one agricultural consumer education program.	2.64	Agree
4	Hear or see advertisements about agricultural consumer education on radio or television.	2.62	Agree
5	The frequency of agricultural consumer education programs is adequate	2.50	Agree
6	Aware of agricultural consumer education programs in my area.	2.44	Disagree

The results in Table 2 on the level of participation in consumer education programs revealed that respondents moderately engaged in the available programs. The statement that the information from consumer education programs is easy to understand and apply recorded a mean score of 2.88, indicating that most respondents found the programs comprehensible and practical. Similarly, the statement that participation in these programs has increased interest in agricultural products had a mean of 2.82. The result further showed that respondents have personally participated in at least one agricultural consumer education program, with a mean score of 2.64. The frequency of agricultural consumer education programs was rated adequate, with a mean of 2.50, which is the minimum level for acceptance

Table 3: Mean Response on Impact of Consumer Education on Behaviour

S/N	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1	Prefer locally produced agricultural goods based on consumer awareness campaigns.	3.23	Agree
2	Consumer education has reduced my likelihood of purchasing unsafe or adulterated products.	3.20	Agree
3	Consumer education programs have helped to make informed choices about agricultural products.	3.18	Agree
4	Check labeling and expiry dates when buying agricultural products.	3.01	Agree
5	Give more attention to product quality and hygiene after attending education programs.	3.01	Agree
6	Consumer education has improved people's trust in agricultural product information.	3.0	Agree

In Table 3, the study also assessed the impact of consumer education on consumer behaviour, and the findings revealed a clear positive influence. Respondents strongly agreed that they prefer locally produced agricultural goods due to consumer education campaigns, as this statement recorded the highest mean of 3.23. Similarly, the statement that consumer education has reduced the likelihood of purchasing unsafe or adulterated products had a mean of 3.20. The statement that consumer education programs have helped respondents make informed choices about agricultural products recorded a mean of 3.18. Furthermore, the results revealed that respondents now consider labeling and expiry dates when buying agricultural products, with a mean of 3.01. Equally, the statement that respondents pay more attention to product quality and hygiene after attending education programs also had a mean of 3.01. Lastly, the statement that consumer education has improved trust in agricultural product information recorded a mean of 3.00.

Table 4: Mean responses on Challenges Affecting Effectiveness of consumer Education

S/N	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1	The duration of most education programs is too short to create lasting impact.	3.54	Agree
2	Unawareness of existing agricultural education programs	3.24	Agree
3	Consumers are often not motivated to attend education programs.	3.03	Agree
4	Inadequate publicity reduces public participation in education programs.	3.03	Agree
5	Limited access to media and extension services hinders consumer awareness	3.02	Agree
6	Lack of trained personnel affects the quality of consumer education delivery.	2.91	Agree
7	There is limited funding for consumer education programs.	2.88	Agree

In Table 4, the study identified several challenges that affect the effectiveness of consumer education programs in Makurdi Metropolis. The statement that the duration of most education programs is too short to create a lasting impact recorded the highest mean of 3.54. Respondents also agreed that unawareness of existing agricultural education programs is a significant challenge, with a mean score of 3.24. The statement that consumers are often not motivated to attend education programs had a mean of 3.03, while the statement that inadequate publicity reduces public participation in education programs also recorded a mean of 3.03.

Table 5: Mean responses on Strategies for Improvement of Consumer Education

S/N	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1	Collaboration between agricultural extension officers and community leaders can improve program reach.	3.86	Agree
2	Feedback from participants should be collected to improve future education programs	3.50	Agree
3	Consumer education programs should include practical demonstrations and field visits.	3.45	Agree
4	Local leaders and influencers should be involved in promoting consumer rights.	3.35	Agree
5	Consumer education programs should be designed to suit the literacy	3.23	Agree

	level of participants		
6	Consumer education programs should be integrated into school curricula.	3.21	Agree
7	More media campaigns should be used to promote consumer awareness.	3.21	Agree

In Table 5, the results further revealed various strategies for improving the impact and sustainability of consumer education programs. The statement that collaboration between agricultural extension officers and community leaders can improve program reach recorded the highest mean of 3.86. Respondents also agreed that feedback from participants should be collected to improve future education programs, with a mean of 3.50, indicating the need for continuous program evaluation and responsiveness. The statement that consumer education programs should include practical demonstrations and field visits had a mean of 3.45, showing that experiential learning is preferred for better understanding and retention.

3.1 Discussion of findings

Table 1 showed that there were organized programs for consumers on agricultural products in Makurdi Metropolis via radio and television programs. This provided useful information about agricultural products and practices. The respondents largely relied on mass media and organized community initiatives for consumer education and awareness. This was as a result of herdsmen attacks on farmers in the state. The result implied that media-based channels were the most effective means of reaching consumers within the metropolis, reflecting the vital role of communication technologies in information dissemination. This finding agreed with Oranusi *et al.*, (2021), who emphasized that the media serves as a critical platform for consumer protection and education in Nigeria, particularly in sectors like agriculture and pharmaceuticals, where access to formal education is often limited. Similarly, Caraia *et al.*, (2024) found that mass communication platforms, such as television and radio, remain the most trusted and accessible sources of consumer information, particularly in developing regions. He concluded that community-based and media-led campaigns effectively bridge literacy and infrastructural gaps in consumer education. Agricultural extension workers have problems of language communication barriers and they are few in number.

The highest mean score in table 2 was 2.88, recorded for the statement “The information from

consumer education programs was easy to understand and apply.” This finding indicated that despite moderate participation, respondents found the content of consumer education programs clear, practical, and easy to use. The accessibility of educational messages likely contributed to improved engagement and interest in agricultural consumer issues among participants. This aligns with the findings of Yoshii et al., (2023), who reported that simplicity and clarity in consumer education delivery increase comprehension and participation, especially among learners with diverse literacy levels. Similarly, Bashir et al., (2023) found that the effectiveness of consumer education depends heavily on the communication approach and the ability of educators to present complex consumer concepts in relatable and straightforward terms. Page | 163

The highest mean in table 3 was 3.23, which showed that respondents preferred locally produced agricultural goods due to consumer education campaigns.” This was in line with Laverie & Hass (2022), who showed that consumer education positively influenced buying behaviour by encouraging consumers to favor locally made products, likely due to improved awareness of their quality, safety, and economic importance. The finding implied that consumer education not only enhanced product knowledge but also stimulated local economic participation (Lusardi & Steeter, 2023). This finding was in line with Adeoye and Adebisi (2019), who observed that consumer education fosters trust and transparency in agricultural markets, thereby promoting preference for local produce. Similarly, Thøgersen (2025) argued that well-designed consumer education can drive sustainable consumption patterns by shaping consumer values and encouraging environmentally conscious decisions, including preference for local goods.

The highest mean in table 4 was 3.54, corresponding to the statement “The duration of most education programs was too short to create a lasting impact.” This indicated that although consumer education programs existed, their brevity limited their capacity to produce long-term behavioural change. The finding suggested a need for continuity, reinforcement, and more sustained engagement in consumer education efforts. This statement supports the work of Marcon et. al (2022). This outcome is consistent with Mazlan et al., (2024), who reported that short-term consumer education initiatives often fail to instill lasting behavioural transformation because they lack follow-up and continuous reinforcement. Likewise, Umeh and Okeke (2023) found that many agricultural consumer education efforts in Nigeria are episodic and poorly sustained, reducing their long-term effectiveness.

The highest mean score in table 5 was 3.86, representing the collaboration between agricultural extension officers and community leaders could improve program reach. This showed that respondents strongly believed that effective partnerships between professionals and community stakeholders would enhance the accessibility and success of consumer education programs. The finding suggested that community-based collaboration provides cultural relevance, increases trust, and ensures wider dissemination of consumer information. Page | 164

This finding supports the work of Okolo et al., (2020), who emphasized that collaboration between agricultural extension services and community institutions leads to better communication and adoption of agricultural innovations. Similarly, Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, (2022) highlighted that integrating community leadership into extension service delivery enhances rural outreach and the sustainability of educational programs, particularly in agriculture. These studies affirm that cooperative and participatory approaches ensure that consumer education is contextually relevant and effectively delivered. The present study maintained that collaboration remains a cornerstone in successful consumer education programmes.

4. Conclusion

The findings of the study showed that consumer education significantly influenced consumer awareness and behaviour in Makurdi. The ease of understanding and application of consumer education programs enhanced participation, in practical content that encouraged greater engagement among respondents. The programs also positively influenced consumer behaviour by promoting preference for locally produced agricultural goods, indicating that consumer education fostered economic consciousness and support for local farmers.

However, the study found that the short duration of most programs limited their long-term effectiveness, while inadequate funding, low motivation, and poor publicity further reduced their impact. It was also discovered that collaboration between agricultural extension officers and community leaders offered the most effective strategy for improving program reach and relevance. Overall, the study concluded that consumer education in Makurdi Metropolis was impactful but required improved continuity, coordination, and community participation to achieve sustainable results.

Recommendations

1. Short duration programs should be established between agricultural extension officers and community leaders to improve the reach, cultural relevance, and overall effectiveness of consumer education programs in Makurdi Metropolis.
2. The duration of consumer education programs should be extended and made continuous to ensure that participants retain information and experience lasting behavioural change.
3. Consumer education campaigns should continue to encourage preference for locally produced agricultural goods, as this promotes economic growth, product trust, and sustainable consumption.
4. More emphasis should be placed on radio, television, and organized outreach programs since they have proven to be the most effective channels for spreading consumer education messages.
5. Consumer education materials should be designed in simple, clear, and practical formats, using local languages and relatable examples to enhance understanding among all literacy levels.

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